

Sensitive Base Theory in Women Career Management

Khled Benshina*

ABSTRACT

The concept of glass roof syndrome has been developed in order to define the difficulties women can experience in career processes. This concept demonstrates how women can face problems in their careers and this is a gender distinction. The concept reveals that there are actually no ways to rise that seem to exist, and that women are therefore not easy to rise at work, and that this is the structural reasons Küçük (2018). In short, the sensitive floor the or y refers to the approach to management tasks via considering that women would want to spend less time working because of their strong love for their children, spouse and family, due to the sensitivity of their home. The aim of this study is to share sensitive Base theory for the first time theoretically, to share the data obtained as a basis forth is theory and to present the subject with theoretical and field research-based data. Within the scope of the study, a face-to-face survey will be conducted on women working at the University. In this study, a sensitive Base line scale will be used in a woman's career based on the five Likert scale developed via the author in charge. At this stage, the importance levels of expressions will be determined, so that women workers ' perspectives on career will be evaluated.

As a result of this study, it will be determined that women lead their career to other areas not only with different obstacles but also with women's instinct. Thus, the policies to be produced and the solutions to be implemented will be able to contribute to this context.

Key words: Glass Ceiling Syndrome, Sensitive Base Theory, Female Career.

JEL Code: R40

* Faculty of Tourism and Hotels Tripoly, Libian, khalid72bo@gmail.com

Kadın Kariyer Yönetiminde Hassas Taban Teorisi

Özet

Cam tavan sendromu kavramı, kadınların kariyer süreçlerinde yaşayabileceği zorlukları tanımlamak için geliştirilmiştir. Hassas taban kavramı, kadınların kariyerlerinde cinsiyet ayrımı sayılabacak sorunlarla karşı karşıya kalabileceğini fakat, aslında yükselmenin belirtildiği gibi bir engel ötesinde yapısal nedenleri olduğunu ve kadınların bu nedenle işyerinde yönetici olmak istemeyeceklerini ortaya koymaktadır (Küçük, 2018). Kısacası, hassas zemin teorisi kadınların evlerine olan duyarlılığı, çocukları, eş ve aile için güçlü sevgi nedeniyle çalışmaya daha az zaman harcama isteği nedeniyle yönetim görevlerine mesafeli durması yaklaşımını ifade eder.

Bu çalışmanın amacı, temel teoriyi ilk kez teorik olarak paylaşmak, elde edilen verileri temel olarak paylaşmak, ve konuyu teorik ve alan araştırma tabanlı verilerle sunmaktır. Çalışma kapsamında, Üniversitede çalışan kadınlar üzerinde yüz yüze bir anket yapılacaktır. Bu çalışmada, sorumlu yazar tarafından geliştirilen beş Likert ölçeğine dayanan bir kadının kariyerinde hassas bir temel çizgi ölçeği kullanılacaktır. Bu aşamada, kadın çalışanları kariyer perspektifleri değerlendirilecek şekilde ifadelerin önem düzeyleri belirlenecektir.

Bu çalışmanın bir sonucu olarak, kadınların kariyerlerini sadece farklı engellerle değil, aynı zamanda kadın içgüdüğü ile de diğer alanlara yönlendirdiği belirlenmiştir. Böylece üretilecek politikalar ve uygulanacak çözümler bu bağlamda katkıda bulunabilir.

1. Introduction

Different evaluations can be made about career in terms of professional achievement and there may be some difficulties in the course of progress or development or in the course of time. Glass Ceiling Syndrome is a syndrome in which women are exposed to a variety of conditions, such as ascents, careers, invisible obstacles, gender discrimination, mobbing, there are a number of barriers to women's career in terms of factors and in this respect women are defined as disadvantaged compared to men. In this respect, it is stated that women cannot make a career or rise in their duties due to some obstacles Women are more emotional than men, they will experience events over and over again, and they have an empathy that can hear their psychological distress and resentment in almost the same way every remembrance.

According to Küçük (2018) he appreciate that women can face problems in their careers and this is a gender distinction. The concept reveals that there are actually no ways to rise that seem to exist, and that women are therefore not easy to rise at work, and that this is the structural reasons.

The fact that women can work via spending fewer hours due to home sensitivity due to their strong love for their children, their parents and their family depending on their maternal consciousness, preferring jobs that can devote time to their home, besides they are more sensitive about affection and feelings than men the emotional intensity that can be experienced via the groups affected via the blackout in the decision-making stages due to the fact that they are not interested in the management duties considering that they will continue to have a certain effect in the future periods.

2. Aims of Study

The aims of research to offer sensitive base in theory compared in public and private sector .

The scope of study was in two vocational schools in Ankara and the administrative units of the university.

60 questionnaires were distributed, of which 45 were received.

3. Scope of Study and Methodology

Methodology: Public and private sector

The data obtained has been exchanged with levels of importance through the validity and reliability test (Küçük, 2018). there likert scale 5 agree this agree

4. Model and Hypothesis

The model of the study is shown in Figure (1)

Figure 1. Model of Study

H1: there is no difference between the women in public sector and private sector want to be manager

H2: there is a difference between the women married and single want to be manager

H3: there is a difference between the women have children and dont hhave children wont to be manager

H4: there is a difference between the women have children Less than 8 years and More than 16 years old wont to be manager.

as seen in Figure 1. there is no difference between public sector and private sector. So our hypotheses registered that

H1: There is there is no difference between public sector and private sector. so our hypotheses registered that.

5. Data Analysis

The first table shows that frequency of demography and the sample of the research seen.

Table 1. Frequency of the Sample

	Items	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Marital Status	married	22	71.0
	single	9	29.0
Children	I have	18	58.1
	I don't have	13	41.9
Age Children	Younger than 8 years	21	46.7
	Over 16 year	24	53.3
Function	Private sector	18	40.0
	Public sector	27	60.0

The first table shows the social status of the sample of the research as well as the percentage of frequency of the sample. The table also shows the percentage of married and unmarried women, as well as the percentage of women with children, children and children. The last paragraph in the table showing the type of work for the research sample. Are these women engaged in special work or public work? All this detail exists in the repetition for the sample and percentages. All these data help in reaching a real understanding

of the problems and obstacles facing the female worker in the Anatolian platea (Küçük, 2016, p. 230).

Table 2. Shows that factor analysis of women tend to be managers

Women's Tendency to Become Administrators Factors	Factor Load	Core value	Variance Explanation Rate(%)	Cronbach Alfa	Average	KMO value
1. Despite the completion of the faculty, women who are not involved in a job and are interested in their home are more than men.	4,176	4,176 2,382 1,130	69,886	0,841	3,51	,631
2. Despite having a certain level of expertise, certification and competence, women who are not involved in a job but are interested in their home are more likely than men.	2,382				3,56	
3. Even though there are workable jobs, women who are not working in a job and are interested in their home are more than men.	1,130				3,51	
4. Women are more willing to work part time than men because of their responsibilities	,887				3,78	
5. Women are eager to retire earlier than men.	,677				3,36	
6. Women are eager to spend time at home, according to men.	,482				3,00	
7. Women are eager to spend time with their children, according to men.	,393				3,56	
8. Women are less willing to be managers than men because of the need for intensive work.	,360				3,82	
9. Women are less eager to be managers than men because they will be more emotionally influenced via the decisions they will make as managers.	,263				2,29	
10. Women are less eager to be managers than men because they spend more time outside the home due to travel and meetings.	,159				3,00	
11. Married, child-based women may be less willing to become managers than single- or childless women.	,091				3,07	

As shown in Table A-1.4., the value of Kaiser-MeyerOlkin (KMO) was found to be 0.631. Since this value is over 0.4 or even 0.5, it is shown that sampling is sufficient and meaningful factors can be obtained from research data. The fact that all expressions have a factor load greater than 0.5 and an eigenvalue greater than 1 indicate that the expressions are suitable for use in analysis. The Cronbach's alpha coefficient was 0.841. Since this value is greater than 0.80, the scale is highly reliable and the variance explanation rate is 69,886%. Thus, it was decided that the scale could be used in scientific research (Küçük, 2016, p. 232). According to the results of the research, since the importance level of most of the scales included in the scale is amongst 3.67 and 5.00, it has been evaluated that the expressions in the measure are mostly accepted via the participants. "Women are less willing to be managers than men because they spend more time outside the home because of travel and meetings" (3,00). "Women are less eager to be managers than men because they are more emotionally influenced via decisions they make. "(2,29) and" women are less willing to be managers than men because of the need for intensive work of the manager "(3,82) are of moderate importance 2,33-3,66 (Küçük, 2016: 228-231; Kalaycı, 2010: 405).

Table 3. Mean and Standard Deviation of Sample

One-Sample Statistics				
	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
married	45	1.52	.504	.074
children	45	1.51	.506	.075
age	45	1.53	.505	.075
fansion	45	1.60	.495	.074

Table 4. T test

One-Sample Test

	Test Value = 95					
	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
					Lower	Upper
married	-1244.742	44	.000	-93.489	-93.61	-93.34
children	-1240.577	44	.000	-93.489	-93.64	-93.34
age	-1242.740	44	.000	-93.467	-93.62	-93.32
fancion	-1264.642	44	.000	-93.400	-93.55	-93.25

According to Sample Test analysis there is no difference between the women in public sector and private sector want to be manager H1, it strongly relationship so there is strongly relationship the alternative hypothesis " is accepted . And the hypotheses H2, H3, H4 were accepted (Küçük, 2016.)

6. Discussion

According to the result of table 1.1 the marital state of the women are the majority of the participants are married which 71% from the target sample and 29 % from the participants are single. And also according to the demographical frequency of the participants are having children which remain 58 % and 41 % from the participants they do not have children which reflects that most of the working women are in marital state and they also have children which as Flora, (1998) he announced that Women’s participation in economic and public life strengthens economic growth, equitable governance and public trust, from the community level to top policymaking circles (Küçük, 2016, p. 231).

Also as White, (1995) demonstrated that women can be working and a house wife at the same time and this study result can be similar to his investigation. According to this study women's Tendency to Become Administrators Factors has a completion of the faculty, women who are not involved in a job and are interested in their home are more than men which remains high value of rate 69,886 %. Also, a certain level of expertise, certification and competence,

women who are not involved in a job but are interested in their home are more likely than men in rate 0% which similar to (Flora, (1998); (White, 1995).

The value of women whose working in the private sector is balanced with women whose working in the public sector which means that there is no variances amongst the sector of the work to the women the most important factor is that women can work and rap money to improve their life style which as (Rahmah et al., 2013).

7. Results

In the survey conducted with the help of the "Women's tendency to become managers" scale; the willingness of women to become managers has been determined to be medium and over. Here the finding of the researcher lowers the expectation that the researcher in general will be able to average the studying of the working women in general without subjecting them to a different separation. If this research is conducted via making a distinction in the form of married-single, separated, children and children, or small and large children, the results are likely to emerge more clearly (Küçük, 2016). The research is limited to this level of analysis but will be developed in future studies to test whether there are statistical variances in the tendency of women to be managers in terms of different variables.

8. Suggestions

- In the light of these conclusions, the following suggestions can be made for labor management and institutional management. Women should be supported via women's emotional intelligence, especially in the sense of the world, and their positions should be supported via those who are suitable and enthusiastic.
- Part time must be opened in front of work.
- Regulations on early retirement should be model*
- Policies should be developed to apply variable overtime in different periods of Life
- Flexible working hours can be developed for women with children*
- Institutional nurseries where working mothers can deal with especially small children should be widespread.

Sensitive Base Theory in Women Career Management (pp.97-108) Khled Benshina

- Early retirement conditions can be observed*
- Home-office applications where women can produce economic value when dealing with their homes and families can be supported and disseminated.
- Researchers can do this work in different organizations, while at the same time female participants can be married, children and small or large. According to these control variables, they can determine whether there is a statistical difference amongst the 50 participants (Küçük, 2016).

Sensitive Base Theory in Women Career Management (pp.97-108) Khled Benshina

REFERENCES

- Arthur M. B. (1994), The Boundaryless Career: A New Perspective for Organizational Inquiry, *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 15, 295–306
- Ashmore, M. R., & Dimitroulopoulou, C. (2009). Personal exposure of children to air pollution. *Atmospheric Environment*, 43(1), 128-141.
- Baker, K. A. (2002). “Carrer women” or “working women”? change versus stability for young Palestinian women in Israel. *The Journal of Israeli History*, 21(1-2), 85-109.
- Betz N. (1993), Women’s Career Development In F. L. Denmark, M. A. Paludi, (eds) *Psychology of Women*.
- Betz N. E., Fitzgerald L. F. (1987), *The Career Psychology of Women*. Academic Press, NY
- Braynion P. (2004), Power and Leadership, *Journal of Health, Organization, and Management*, 18(6), 447–463
- Carnevale, D. G., & Wechsler, B. (1992). Trust in the public sector: Individual and organizational determinants. *Administration & Society*, 23(4), 471-494.
- Cattaneo, A., Peruzzo, C., Garramone, G., Urso, P., Ruggeri, R., Carrer, P., & Cavallo, D. M. (2011). Airborne particulate matter and gaseous air pollutants in residential structures in Lodi province, Italy. *Indoor Air*, 21(6), 489-500.
- Developent. *Journal of Heilongjiang Administrative Cadre College of Politics and Law*, 4, 048.
- Englund, J. A., Baker, C. J., Raskino, C., McKinney, R. E., Petrie, B., Fowler, M. G., ... & Schliozberg, J. (1997). Zidovudine, didanosine, or both as the initial treatment for symptomatic HIV-infected children. *New England Journal of Medicine*, 336(24), 1704-1712.
- Flora, J. L. (1998). Social capital and communities of place. *Rural sociology*, 63(4), 481-506.
- Havva Çaha, E. Sare Aydın Yılmaz ve Ömer Çaha. (2016) *Türkiye’de Cam Tavan Sendromu Hizmet Sektöründe Kadın*, KADEM Yayınları, İstanbul.
- Kotzias, D., Koistinen, K., Kephelopoulos, S., Schlitt, C., Carrer, P., Maroni, M., ... & McLaughlin, J. (2005). The INDEX project. Critical Appraisal of the Setting and Implementation of Indoor Exposure Limits in the EU. Final Report. Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union (<http://ec.europa>).
- Küçük, O. (2016). *Bilimsel Araştırma Yöntemleri*. Ekin Yayınevi, Bursa.

Sensitive Base Theory in Women Career Management (pp.97-108) Khled Benshina

- Küçük, O. (2018). Kadınların Kariyer Yönetiminde Hassas Taban Teorisi: Bir Araştırma (The Theory of Women's Sensitive Base in Career Management: A Research), IWSC, İstanbul, p(75).
- McKeen, C. A., & Burke, R. J. (1992). Work, career and personal characteristics of managerial and professional women: Description, interpretations and implications. *International Review of Sociology*, 3(3), 6-42.
- Mengersen, K., Morawska, L., Wang, H., Murphy, N., Tayphasavanh, F., Darasavong, K., & Holmes, N. S. (2011). Association between indoor air pollution measurements and respiratory health in women and children in Lao PDR. *Indoor air*, 21(1), 25-35.
- Nineteenth-Twentieth Century France. DUODA: estudis de la diferència sexual, (1), 41-58.
- Örücü, E., Kılıç, R. ve Kılıç T. (2007). "Cam Tavan Sendromu ve Kadınların Üst Düzey Yönetici Pozisyonuna Yükselmelerindeki Engeller: Balıkesir İli Örneği", *Celal Bayar Üni. İİBF Yönetim ve Ekonomi Dergisi*, 14, (2), 117-135
- Pascarella, E. T., & Terenzini, P. T. (1991). *How college affects students* (Vol. 1991). San Francisco: Jossey-Bass.
- Rahmah, N., Jusoff, K., Heliawaty, M., Monim, Y., Batoa, H., & Nalefo, L. (2013). The Role of Women in Public Sector and Family Welfare. *World Applied Sciences Journal*, 26, 72-76.
- Raian van den bergh (2012) "Highly skilled migrant women: a career development framework", *Journal of Management Development*, Vol. 31 Issue: 2, pp.142-158 ,
- Shaw, D. (2006). Women's right to health and the Millennium Development Goals: Promoting partnerships to improve access. *International Journal of Gynecology & Obstetrics*, 94(3), 207-215.
- Solomon, CharleneMarmet, (2000). 'Cracks in the GlassCeiling', *Workforce*, 79 (9), ss. 87-90 ,
- Son, J., & Kim, E. (2014). The Effect of Work-Family Reconciliation Policy on Intention to Keep Working of Working Mother with Children. *Korean Journal of Human Ecology*, 23(3), 421-441.
- Tilly, L. A. (1990). *Labor Markets, Women Workers and the State: Refelections on Public and Private in Wolf, N. (2013). Fire with fire: New female power and how it will change the twenty-first century. Random House.*

*Sensitive Base Theory in Women Career Management (pp.97-108) Khled
Benshina*

Waldfogel, J. (2002). Child care, women's employment, and child outcomes. *Journal of Population Economics*, 15(3), 527-548.

White, B. (1995). The career development of successful women. *Women in Management Review*, 10(3), 4-15.

Xuan-yuan, W. U. (2010). Employment of Female Students and Professional Career Developent. *Journal of Heilongjiang Administrative Cadre College of Politics and Law*, 4, 048.

Xuan-yuan, W. U. (2010). Employment of Female Students and Professional Career.

